

R_{Teo} = the processing range of the exterior ring;

R_{Tio} = the processing range of the interior ring;

The T_i position of the center of the interior ring from the stated benchmark will have the following coordinates:

$$\begin{cases} X_{T_i} = (R_{Teo} + R_{Tio} - 2r) \sin \alpha \\ Y_{T_i} = (R_{Teo} + R_{Tio} - 2r) \cos \alpha \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

ANALYSIS OF THE AXIAL RIGIDITY. ESTABLISHING A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR THE SIMULATION.

In dynamic mode, the bearing's vibrations will produce relative movements between the interior and the exterior rings. It is considered a movement of the interior ring equal to u_1 .

This is equivalent to a displacement of the interior ring center along T_x axis with a distance equal to u_1 . The T_i point will become T_i' point, which has the following coordinates:

$$\begin{cases} X_{T_i'} = X_{T_i} + u_1 = (R_{Teo} + R_{Tio} - 2r) \sin \alpha + u_1 \\ Y_{T_i'} = Y_{T_i} = (R_{Teo} + R_{Tio} - 2r) \cos \alpha \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

This will produce a displacement of the bead (of its center), its deformation and the runways deformation. We can write:

$$\begin{cases} X_{T_i'} = (R_e - r) \sin \alpha_e + (R_i - r) \sin \alpha_i \\ Y_{T_i'} = (R_e - r) \cos \alpha_e + (R_i - r) \cos \alpha_i \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

By making simplifications, we have:

Figure 2. Technological elements of construction for the bearing in case of dynamic stress;

The angle at contact with the rings will become:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_i = \alpha + \varphi_i \\ \alpha_e = \alpha + \varphi_e \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The rings deformation will be produced under F_e and F_i forces action; these forces are calculated using the following relations, based on the Hertzian contact theory:

$$\begin{cases} F_i = K(R_i - R_i^0) = K \cdot \Delta_i \\ F_e = K(R_e - R_e^0) = K \cdot \Delta_e \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where K is a constant which depends on the nature of the materials being in contact, while Δ_i and Δ_e are the interior, respectively the exterior ring deformations.

In order to analyze the k_{11} rigidity variation, first of all, we will study the effect of the bearing rotation movement. For this, we must solve the system (5) for an $u_1=0$ movement. We will have the solutions:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_i &= \frac{-2(R_{T_{i0}}-r)tg\alpha}{R_{T_{i0}}-R_{T_{e0}}} & \varphi_e &= \frac{2(R_{T_{e0}}-r)tg\alpha}{R_{T_{i0}}-R_{T_{e0}}} \\ \Delta_i &= -\frac{D\Omega^2\cos\alpha}{2k} & \Delta_e &= \frac{D\Omega^2\cos\alpha}{2k} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Where: } D = m_b |R_{T_{e0}} \cdot r \cos\alpha| B^2 \quad (8)$$

The interaction between the bead and the interior ring (respectively the exterior ring) will be:

$$\begin{aligned} F_i &= -\frac{D\Omega^2\cos\alpha}{2} \\ F_e &= \frac{D\Omega^2\cos\alpha}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By introducing a longitudinal displacement u_1 , the bead will continuously deform the rings, with the shifts $\Delta_i \rightarrow \Delta_i + \Delta_{it}$ and $\Delta_e \rightarrow \Delta_e + \Delta_{et}$, while the rotations are $\varphi_i \rightarrow \varphi_i + \varphi_{it}$ and $\varphi_e \rightarrow \varphi_e + \varphi_{et}$.

The system becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \sin\alpha\Delta_i^I + \sin\alpha\Delta_e^I + (R_{T_{i0}} - \Delta_i - r)\cos\alpha\varphi_i^I + (R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\cos\alpha\varphi_e^I = u_1 \\ \cos\alpha\Delta_i^I + \cos\alpha\Delta_e^I - (R_{T_{i0}} - \Delta_i - r)\sin\alpha\varphi_i^I - (R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\sin\alpha\varphi_e^I = 0 \\ k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_i\cos\alpha)\Delta_i^I - k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e\cos\alpha)\Delta_e^I + F\cos\alpha\varphi_i^I + F\cos\alpha\varphi_e^I = 0 \\ k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_i\sin\alpha)\Delta_i^I - k(\cos\alpha + \varphi_e\sin\alpha)\Delta_e^I - F\sin\alpha\varphi_i^I - F\sin\alpha\varphi_e^I = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

This is a linear system with the unknown Δ_i , Δ_e , φ_i , φ_e , where:

$$\Delta_i^I = \frac{m_1}{m}; \quad \Delta_e^I = \frac{m_2}{m}; \quad \varphi_i^I = \frac{m_3}{m}; \quad \varphi_e^I = \frac{m_4}{m}; \quad (11)$$

Also, the axial force, which determines the u_1 displacement, is calculated using eq. (12)

$$\begin{aligned} F_{ax} &= n \cdot k \cdot \Delta_i^I (\sin\alpha + (\varphi_i + \varphi_i^I)\cos\alpha) \\ F_{ax} &= n \cdot k \cdot \frac{d_1}{m} u_1 (\sin\alpha + (\varphi_i + \frac{d_3}{m} u_1)\cos\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

And the rigidity

$$\begin{aligned} k_{11} &= \frac{\delta F_{ax}}{\delta u_1} & (13) \\ m_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} u_1 & \sin\alpha & (R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\cos\alpha & (R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\cos\alpha \\ 0 & \cos\alpha & -(R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\sin\alpha & -(R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\sin\alpha \\ 0 & -k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & F\cos\alpha & F\cos\alpha \\ 0 & -k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & -F\sin\alpha & -F\sin\alpha \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} \sin\alpha & u_1 & (R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\cos\alpha & (R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\cos\alpha \\ \cos\alpha & 0 & -(R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\sin\alpha & -(R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\sin\alpha \\ k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & 0 & F\cos\alpha & F\cos\alpha \\ k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & 0 & -F\sin\alpha & -F\sin\alpha \end{bmatrix} \\
 m_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} \sin\alpha & \sin\alpha & u_1 & (R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\cos\alpha \\ \cos\alpha & \cos\alpha & 0 & -(R_{T_{e0}} + \Delta_e - r)\sin\alpha \\ k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & -k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & 0 & F\cos\alpha \\ k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & -k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & 0 & -F\sin\alpha \end{bmatrix} \\
 m_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} \sin\alpha & \sin\alpha & (R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\cos\alpha & u_1 \\ \cos\alpha & \cos\alpha & -(R_{T_{i0}} + \Delta_i - r)\sin\alpha & 0 \\ k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & -k(\sin\alpha + \varphi_e \cos\alpha) & F\cos\alpha & 0 \\ k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & -k(\cos\alpha - \varphi_e \sin\alpha) & -F\sin\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

We have:

$$k_{11} = M + 2 \cdot N \cdot u_1$$

$$M = n \cdot k \cdot \frac{d_1}{m} (\sin\alpha + \varphi_i \cos\alpha)$$

$$N = n \cdot k \cdot \frac{d_1 \cdot d_3}{m^2} \cdot \cos\alpha$$

$$k_{11} = \sqrt{M^2 + 4NF_{ax}}$$

$$m = 2kF \left[R_{T_{i0}} - R_{T_{e0}} - \frac{\Omega^2 \cos\alpha}{k} m_b (R_{T_{e0}} - r \cos\alpha) \frac{(R_e - 2r \cos\alpha - d)^2}{4 \cdot (R_e - r \cos\alpha - d)^2} \right]$$

$$d_1 = kF \sin\alpha \left[R_{T_{i0}} - R_{T_{e0}} - \frac{\Omega^2 \cos\alpha}{k} m_b (R_{T_{e0}} - r \cos\alpha) \frac{(R_e - 2r \cos\alpha - d)^2}{4 \cdot (R_e - r \cos\alpha - d)^2} \right]$$

$$d_3 = 2kF \cos\alpha + 2k^2 \sin\alpha \cdot \operatorname{tg}\alpha \cdot \left[R_{T_{i0}} - R_{T_{e0}} - \frac{\Omega^2 \cos\alpha}{k} m_b (R_{T_{e0}} - r \cos\alpha) \frac{(R_e - 2r \cos\alpha - d)^2}{4 \cdot (R_e - r \cos\alpha - d)^2} \right]$$

(15)

By calculating M and N, we have:

$$C_1 = \frac{nk \sin 2\alpha}{F} \cdot [F \cos\alpha + k \sin\alpha \cdot \operatorname{tg}\alpha \cdot (R_{T_{e0}} - r)]$$

$$C_2 = \frac{nk \sin 2\alpha}{F} \cdot \frac{\sin^2 \alpha}{8} \cdot \frac{(R_{T_{e0}} - 2r \cos\alpha)^2}{R_{T_{e0}} - r \cos\alpha}$$

$$C_3 = \frac{m_b \cos\alpha}{4k} \cdot \frac{(R_{T_{e0}} - 2r \cos\alpha)^2}{R_{T_{e0}} - r \cos\alpha}$$

$$k_{11} = \sqrt{M^2 + 4 \cdot \frac{C_1 + C_2 \cdot \Omega^2}{-C_3 \cdot \Omega^2} \cdot F_{ax}}$$

$$A_1 = \frac{4C_1}{C_3}; A_2 = \frac{4C_2}{C_3}$$

$$k_{11} = \sqrt{M^2 - \left(\frac{A_1}{\Omega^2} + A_2\right) \cdot F_{ax}}$$

(16)

For the purpose of establishing a mathematical model for the simulation, it is considered the expression of the dynamic accommodation base load at the rolling contact, which is given by the relation:

$$Q_C = A \cdot \left[\frac{D_R \cdot D_{C_{i,e}}}{D_w \cdot (D_{C_{i,e}} - D_R)} \right]^{0,41} \cdot \frac{(1 \pm \gamma)^{1,39}}{(1 \pm \gamma)^{1/3}} \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma}{\cos \alpha} \right)^{0,3} \cdot D_w^{1,8} \cdot Z^{-1/3} \quad (17)$$

Where:

Q_C = the basis dynamic load at the rolling contact, for bearings with contact point [N];

A = material constant = 100;

D_R = the double of the curvature radius of the rolling body in the area of contact with the rolling track;

$D_{C_{i,e}}$ = the diameter of the rolling track of the interior/ exterior ring;

D_w = the diameter of the rolling body;

[4, 6, 7, 8]

The simulation was done using MATLAB MathWorks for two typo dimensions of angular contact bearings with beads. The constructive dimensions are given in Table 1 [6].

Table 1. The constructive dimensions used in the mathematical simulation of the models;

d (mm)	A	D_R (mm)	D_{C_i} (mm)	D_w (mm)	γ	d_m (mm)	α^0	Y	Q_C (N)	n
40	100	10,16	46	7,94	0,142	53,94	15	1	3298,68	16
25	100	8,62	31	6,75	0,159	41	15	1	2650,97	14

The resulting mathematical models for each case are given by the following expressions:

$$k_{11} = \sqrt{18438 - \left(\frac{7265104,8}{\Omega^2} + 1403,39 \right) F_{ax}}$$

$$k_{11} = \sqrt{7377,766 - \left(\frac{3450741}{\Omega^2} + 1046,956 \right) F_{ax}}$$

(18)

The simulations were done by varying the definition domain of the two parameters $n_\Omega = 15100 \div 19000$ r/m and $F_{ax} = 1 \div 10$ (N), corresponding to the results obtained by direct measurements. The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3- Analysis of bearing axial rigidity in case of the main axis from high rotation speed technological systems;

CONCLUSION

- 1) The simulations were made for materials for processing like steel, cast iron and bronze;
- 2) The range of the interior grinding spindle angular speed corresponds to the direct experimental measurement ranges:

$$n_{w1} = 15100 \frac{r}{m}; n_{w2} = 17500 \frac{r}{m}; n_{w3} = 19000 \frac{r}{m};$$

- 3) The spindle's final load range corresponds to the direct experimental measurement ranges:

$$F_{ax steel} = 0 \div 10 (N); F_{ax cast iron} = 1 \div 4 (N); F_{ax bronze} = 1 \div 6 (N);$$

- 4) In both cases one can observe a decrease of the axial rigidity with the increase of the final load, with a higher gradient for the real model than the one obtained after the simulation;
- 5) The axial rigidity remains constant or varies very little with the variation of the angular speed of the interior grinding spindle axis.

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